

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

13 thematic roundtables on policy recommendations

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Migration ImpAct assessment To Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European rural and mountain regions

13 thematic roundtables on policy recommendations

Call: H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2019

Work Programmes:

H2020-EU.3.6.1.1. The mechanisms to promote smart, sustainable and inclusive growth

H2020-EU.3.6.1.2. Trusted organisations, practices, services and policies that are necessary to build resilient, inclusive, participatory, open and creative societies in Europe, in particular taking into account migration, integration and demographic change

Deliverable 7.12: 13 thematic roundtables on policy recommendations

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Introduction

In WP6.2 policy recommendations have been developed based on empirical findings, a literature review and SWOT-analyses for different government levels in a participatory process together with different local, regional and national stakeholders. Together with, e.g., policy makers, public administration staff, migrants and migrant communities, education providers, representative bodies and employers, the pre-validated policy recommendations have been discussed, supplemented and validated in roundtables. In this sense, the conducted policy roundtables were of high importance in the evaluation, elaboration and validation process of the policy recommendations and solutions, which are also collected in the Booklet with MATILDE policy recommendations (Deliverable D7.13), ensuring a wider spread of the policy recommendations and solutions provided by MATILDE. Based on the elaborated and validated policy recommendations, further roundtables and dissemination events were held in WP7 (Deliverable D7.12), devoted to present and share the policy recommendations with local and regional stakeholders (as defined in the MATILDE Stakeholder Involvement Plan, Gruber et al. 2020). The policy recommendations were discussed in light of practical needs and observations, i.e., with practitioners, entrepreneurs, employers and their representative bodies, migrants' organizations, public service providers, and policy makers at the regional level during thematic roundtables in the 13 regions covered by MATILDE.

The following documentation is a condensed overview of those roundtables and events, where the most important key data such as attendance, a description of the representation as well as a photo documentation are presented.

Bibliography: Gruber, M., Lobnig, C., Scheiflinger, S. and Stainer-Hämmerle, K. (2020): Stakeholder involvement plan. MATILDE Deliverable 2.8. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4005933.

Roundtables

Overview

Case Study Region	Venue	Date	No. of Participants	Research Partner	Implementation confirmed by the following person	Photos
Carinthia (AT)	1. Villach 2. Villach (inter-regional)	1. 25 th April 2022 2. 11 th November 2022	1. 46 2. 146	CUAS	Marika Gruber	Yes, see attached
Vorarlberg (AT)	1. Bludenz 2. Bludenz 3. Villach (inter-regional)	1. 17 th March 2022 2. 10 th June 2022 3. 11 th November 2022	1. 4 2. 23 3. 146	BAB	Lisa Bauchinger	Yes, see attached
Haskovo (BG)	1. Harmanli 2. Sofia (national)	1. 14-15 th April 2022 2. 22 nd October 2022	1. 46 2. 100+	NBU	Chaya Koleva, Vanina Ninova	Yes, see attached
North Karelia (FI)	1. Lieksa 2. Kitee	1. 9 th May 2022 2. 5 th May 2022	1. ~20 2. 6	UEF	Lauri Havukainen	No pictures available
Ostrobothnia (FI)	Helsinki (national)	13 th September 2022	8	UEF	Lauri Havukainen	No pictures available

Bavaria (DE)	1. Berlin for Bavaria (inter-national) 2. Bernried am Starnberger See	1. 6 th September 2022 2. 26 th April 2022	1. 15 2. 80	FAU	Tobias Weidinger	Yes, see attached
Province of Bolzano (IT)	Online	22 nd March 2022	11	UNITO	Monica Gilli	Yes, see attached
Turin (IT)	1. Online 2. Online (national) 3. Online	1. 1 st March 2022 2. 10 th March 2022 3. 22 nd March 2022	1. 10 2. 10	UNITO	Monica Gilli	Yes, see attached
Gudbrandsdalen (NO)	1. Online 2. Online 3. Online (national)	1. 21 st January 2022 2. 22 nd March 2022 3. 9 th March 2022	1. 11 2. 4 3. 7	INN	Veronica Blumenthal	PowerPoint slides, see attached
Huesca (ES)	1. Online 2. Online 3. Online (national) 4. Online (national)	1. 27 th April 2022 2. 3 rd May 2022 3. 7 th April 2022 4. 12 th May 2022	1. 7 2. 7 3. 16 4. 6	UNIZAR	Raúl Lardiés Bosque	Yes, see attached
Dalarna (SE)	1. Online 2. Online 3. Vansbro 4. Online (national)	1. 26 th April 2022 2. 29 th April 2022 3. 11 th April 2022 4. 29 th April 2022	1. 4 2. 4 3. +10 4. 3	UU	Susanne Stenbacka, Tina Mathiesen, Ulf Hansson, Zuzana Macuchova	No, due to Online-Setting

Bursa (TR)	1. Karacabey 2. Istanbul (national)	1. 27 th October 2021 2. 12 th May 2022	1. 15 2. 28	BILGI	Fatma Yilmaz- Elmas	Yes, see attached
Outer Hebrides & North Ayrshire (UK, Scotland)	Online (national)	27 th October 2022	35	UNIPR	Michele Bianchi	Invitation poster, see attached

Participants

	Associations & Clubs	Asylum & refugee care	Education & training institution	EU-level umbrella organisations	Internal stakeholders	Local Partner	NGOs	Non-organised/other interest groups	Political decision makers	Private businesses	Public administrations	Public welfare service providers	Research facilities and individual researchers	Trade and labour unions and organized representative groups
Carinthia (AT)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Vorarlberg (AT)		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X
Haskovo (BG)		X	X		X	X	X	X	X		X		X	

North Karelia (FI)	X		X					X	X			X		X
Ostrobothnia (FI)									X		X	X		X
Bavaria (DE)	X		X			X		X	X	X	X		X	X
Province of Bolzano (IT)		X	X			X	X				X			X
Turin (IT)		X									X		X	
Gudbrandsdalen (NO)	X	X			X		X		X		X	X	X	
Huesca (ES)	X		X		X		X	X	X			X		
Dalarna (SE)			X				X		X		X			X
Bursa (TR)				X		X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X
Outer Hebrides & North Ayrshire (UK, Scotland)									X	X	X			X

Photo Documentation

Figure 1: Roundtable Villach, 25th April 2022 (©CUAS)

Figure 2: MATILDE Migration Conference “The Future of Living Together in Rural Areas” in Villach, 11th November 2022 (©CUAS/Anita Bister)

Figure 3: Regional roundtable Bludenz, 17th March 2022 (© BAB)

Figure 4: Regional roundtable Bludenz, 10th June 2022 (© BAB)

Figure 5: Regional roundtable Harmanli, 14th April 2022 (©Ivan Atanasov)

Figure 6: National roundtable Sofia, 22nd October 2022 (©NBU)

Matilde-hankkeen keskustelutilaisuus 9.5.

 Lauri Havukainen
To

pe 22.4.2022 10:35

Reply Reply All Forward

Hei.

Järjestämme Itä-Suomen yliopiston Karjalan Tutkimuslaitoksen Matilde-tutkimushankkeeseen liittyen tutkimustulos- ja palautekeskustelutilaisuuden Lieksassa maanantaina 9.5. klo 12–14. Tilana toimii Metka-talo.

Tarkoitus on käydä läpi hankkeen tuloksia sekä keskustella mahdollisista parannusehdotuksista niin käytännön toimintaan kuin myös poliittisiin päätöksiin.

Tämä kutsu tulee sekä kunnan kotouttamis-, että nuorisopuolelle. Tilaisuuteen pyritään samaan osallistujia myös maahanmuuttajayhteisöistä, kristilliseltä opistoilta ja luterilaiselta seurakunnalta.

Ilmoitattehan pääsystä minulle.

Hankkeen sivut: <https://matilde-migration.eu/>
Hanke yliopiston sivuilla: <https://uefconnect.uef.fi/tutkimusryhma/matilde-migration-impact-assessment-to-enhance-integration-and-local-development-in-european-rural-and-mountain-areas/>

Terveisin,
Lauri Havukainen
Tutkimusavustaja
Karjalan tutkimuslaitos / Matilde-hanke
Itä-Suomen yliopisto

Figure 7: Roundtable Lieksa (Invitation mail), 9th May 2022 (© UEF)

Figure 8: Thematic roundtable Berlin, 6th September 2022 (©Kathrin Zupan)

Figure 9: Roundtable Bussoleno, 1st March 2022 (©UNITO/Monica Gilli)

Figure 10: National Roundtable, 10th March 2022 (©UNITO/Monica Gilli)

Figure 11: Roundtable Bolzano, 22nd March 2022 (©UNITO/Monica Gilli)

FORUM
DISUGUAGLIANZE
DIVERSITÀ

MATILDE

Politiche e buone pratiche a favore dell'inclusione dei nuovi abitanti nei territori montani, rurali ed interni italiani

10 MARZO 2022
15:00 - 17:30

15:00 - 15:20	Obiettivi dell'incontro e presentazione dei partecipanti al tavolo Andrea Mornroff, Co-coordinatore Forum Disuguaglianze e Diversità
15:20 - 15:40	Presentazione del progetto MATILDE e delle raccomandazioni politiche elaborate Andrea Membretti, University of Eastern Finland (UEF)
15:40 - 17:00	Discussione sugli elementi presentati Partecipano: Fabrizio Barca , Co-coordinatore Forum Disuguaglianze e Diversità Marco Bussone , Presidente Uncem Gianfilippo Mignogna , Sindaco del Comune di Biccari (FG) Maria Assunta Rosa , Viceprefetto Ministero dell'Interno Linda Laura Sabbadini , Direttrice centrale ISTAT Moderano: Andrea Membretti Mia Scotti , ricercatrice MATILDE presso l'Università di Torino
17:00 - 17:15	Conclusioni Sabrina Lucatelli, Direttrice di Riabitare l'Italia
17:15 - 17:30	Chiusura del tavolo e follow up Andrea Mornroff

In diretta sul sito e sulla pagina Facebook del Forum Disuguaglianze e Diversità

Figure 12: National roundtable (invitation poster) (©UNITO)

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Migration ImpAct assessment To Enhance
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**Oppsummering
Idéverksted**

Internasjonalt Råd, Tynset, fredag 21 januar
Maria Røhnebæk (INN) & Signe Lise Dahl (IFK)

www.matilde-migration.eu

MATILDE har mottatt
finansiering fra Norges
Landbruks- og matdepartement
og fra Innviir og
regionen i Nord-Østlandet

Figure 13: Roundtable Nord Østerdal (PowerPoint slide), 21st January 2022 (©INN)

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**Policy anbefalinger
basert på resultater
fra MATILDE**

Rundbordsamtale, onsdag 9.mars 2022
Veronica Blumenthal (INN), Signe-Lise Dahl (IFK) & Maria
Røhnebæk (INN)

www.matilde-migration.eu

MATILDE har mottatt
finansiering fra Norges
Landbruks- og matdepartement
og fra Innviir og
regionen i Nord-Østlandet

Figure 14: National Roundtable (PowerPoint slide), 9th March 2022 (©INN)

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Migration ImpAct assessment To Enhance
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European rural and mountain regions

**Oppsummering
Idéverksted**

Faglig forum Midt-Gudbrandsdal, tirsdag 22. mars 2022
Maria Røhnebæk (INN) & Signe-Lise Dahl (IFK)

www.matilde-migration.eu

MATILDE har mottatt
finansiering fra Norges
Landbruks- og matdepartement
og fra Innviir og
regionen i Nord-Østlandet

Figure 15: Roundtable Midt-Gudbrandsdal (PowerPoint slide), 22nd March 2022 (©INN)

Figure 16: Regional roundtable Aragón, 3rd May 2022 (©Raúl Lardiés)

Figure 17: National roundtable Aragón, 12th May 2022 (©Raúl Lardiés)

Figure 18: Roundtable Karacabey, 27th October 2021 (©BILGI)

Figure 19: National roundtable Bursa, 12th May 2022 (©BILGI)

MATILDE MIGRATION POLICY ROUNDTABLE

A Migration Policy for Scottish Rural and Remote
Communities?

THURSDAY, OCTOBER 27TH, 2 PM

Online Meeting

ORGANIZED BY THE UNIVERSITY OF PARMA AND COSLA

Figure 20: National roundtable (Invitation poster) Outer Hebrides, 27th October 2022